

BRAND AWARENESS TOWARDS COUNTERFEITED AND BRANDED PRODUCTS: AS A CONSUMER PROTECTION STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

This is a descriptive type of research to determine the importance of brand awareness strategies to preserve the identity of the original brand from counterfeiting brand of products to identify the original product from the counterfeit product. The results showed that the first to identify the original and counterfeit product the results showed that the respondents are not fully and some are not really satisfied, awareness strategies should be developed by implementing marketing plans such as promotions. The company should conduct seminars for the employee and orientation for the customer. And also, the management should provide an advertisement to educate the customer and the company will conduct a seminar to prevent counterfeiting every 6 months.

Keywords: *Brand awareness, Counterfeited and Branded Products, Consumer Protections*

INTRODUCTION

Counterfeited products or brands is a worldwide problem in today's globalization (Spink et al., 2013). The word brand imitation usually describes copying different branded products. Brand imitation is "any unauthorized manufacturing of goods

whose special characteristics are protected as intellectual property rights (trademarks, patents, and copyrights) constitutes product counterfeiting” (Crettez, Naila, & Georges, 2018). The counterfeits have a good reputation in the market and marketing (Bian & Moutinho, 2011; Jyani & Bansal, 2021). Nowadays, consumers do not know whether it is original or imitation because of packaging is the same.

Jiang and Chen (2021) states that global sales estimates that counterfeit products are almost in the \$650 of billion. Counterfeiting is an enormous problem for businesses all over the world. They imitate products and distribute and sell them at the lowest price. This is a challenge for many marketers around the world. Recent evidence suggested that counterfeit products are prevalent in developing countries. There are some who will dispute about estimates made of \$650 billion do seem high, the level of counterfeiting is present in the global marketplace. Many products come out and many manufacturers are making counterfeit products. The customers are not aware of the brand of the products that they bought if they were imitations or original ones. As time passes by, many manufacturers are making counterfeit products that can be purchased at lower prices. Customers are interested in purchasing a product because of its trademark and its low price.

Research Questions

The aim of the study is to seek answers to be able to develop brand awareness strategies for customers.

Specifically, the study tries to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Occupation
2. How do respondents identify the original product from counterfeit in terms of:
 - 2.1 Price
 - 2.2 Packaging
 - 2.3 Product Texture
3. What are the factors that influence the patronage of counterfeit products in terms of:
 - 3.1 Cost
 - 3.2 Accessibility
 - 3.3 Societal Perception
4. Based on the findings, what strategy will be developed the identity of the original from the counterfeit?
5. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?

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METHODOLOGY

The method used in this study is the Descriptive Research Method. It is a fact-finding study with an adequate and accurate interpretation of the findings. It describes what is emphasized and exists such as current conditions, practices, situations, or any phenomena. The present study or investigation was concerned with the present status of assessing the giving of the branding awareness strategy. The descriptive method of research was one of the most appropriate methods used. In the paper of Ramos (2019), this method is described as a "Fact-finding tool with adequate interpretation." The true collected data according to him should be reported from point of view of the objectives and the basic assumptions of the project underway because it is considered appropriate and relevant to the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data. It is a concern with the current of all existing conditions of the relationship that exists.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The respondents will be the fifty (50) selected consumers in Quezon City. A quota sampling method will be used in this study of the importance of brand awareness strategies to preserve the identity of the original brand from the counterfeiting brand of cosmetic products. A snowball sampling technique is also used in this study.

Description of Respondents

The respondents will be the residents of Quezon City. 50 respondents are consumers of product both counterfeit and original products.

Research Instrument

The primary tool used in this research is the questionnaire, interview, and survey. The data from the questionnaire were supplemented with the data from files and gathered from the responses during the unstructured interview conducted by the researchers.

The questionnaire was made up of four parts:

Part I. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?

The respondents must put their details to know a person's name, gender, age, civil status, educational background, and current status.

Part II. How will the customers identify the original product from the counterfeit product in terms of the following?

The customers will identify through the price because counterfeit is cheaper than the original. Due to mimicking of counterfeit in the original, customers would preferably buy the latter because of its very low price, considering its product name.

Part III. What companies should do to educate customers about genuine products?

To educate the customers about genuine products the company must have advertisements on social media, TV, and the like. The promotion of the product is better.

Part IV. What are the factors that influence the patronage of the counterfeit product?

Manufacturers lack awareness. Manufacturers of original items are not aware that their products are counterfeit, and lack the budget of the consumers. Users tend to buy counterfeit items because of the price. The price of counterfeit items is much lower than the original ones.

Part V. Based on the findings, what strategy will be developed to retain the identity of the original from the counterfeit product?

There will be strategies to retain the original brand from the counterfeit and this will be the output.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher made questions for residents of Quezon City. The researcher started to conduct a survey and give a questionnaire to the respondents of their study. After collecting all the data, the researcher tallied the data.

The result would hopefully be the basis of the importance of brand awareness strategies to preserve the identity of the original brand from counterfeiting brand products.

Finally, the accomplished questionnaires were scored. Results were checked, classified, tabulated, and analyzed. For a clearer visualization and comparison of findings, tables were used in the presentation.

Analysis of Data

The researcher made use of the following statistical tools for a meaningful treatment of data and also to achieve an in-depth interpretation of findings.

Percentage. For the number of respondents and profile frequency counts, percent or rate was used.

The statistical formula is:

$$P = 100 \frac{f}{N}$$

Where:

P	=	Percentage
f	=	frequency
N	=	Number of respondents

Ranking. This was used to show the positional importance of the items that were analyzed.

Weighted Mean. Weighted mean was used to answer the problems raised to identify the product, measures to educate customers and brand awareness strategies.

The formula is:

$$Wm = \frac{\sum xw}{N}$$

Where:

Wm	=	weighted mean
N	=	no. of cases
X	=	frequency
W	=	weight
$\sum xw$	=	summation of frequency times weight

Likert's Scale. Likert's Five-Point Scale rating was used. The weights are assigned to each kind of grouping with their corresponding weights, range and interpretation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section shows the results, the analysis and interpretation of the information gathered from the responses of the respondents from selected area in Quezon City. The presentation of the distinctive tables depended on the different issues in the study.

**Discussion of Results for Demographic Profile of the Respondents
 Respondents Personal Profile According to Gender**

Variable	Respondents	%
Gender		
Male	25	23
Female	25	77
Total	50	100

Figure 4.1 shows the representation of how the respondents are distributed according to their gender. The data shows that 23 or 76.66 percent are female and only 7 or 23.33 percent are male who were participants in this study.

Respondents' Personal Profile According to age

Variable	Respondents	%
Age		
Below 20 years old	10	20
21 – 30 years old	15	30
31 – 40 years old	15	30
41 – 50 years old	10	20
51 – 60 years old	0	0
61 & above	0	0
Total	50	100

Figure 4.2 shows the representation of how the respondents were distributed according to their Age. The data shows that the highest rank are those ages from 21 to 30 years old which has 19 or 63.33% of respondents were many users of cosmetics products. It is followed by below 20 years old which has 7 or 23.33% of respondents. The 3 or 10% of respondents are 31 - 40 years old and lastly, the least number of respondents are ages from 41 –50 with only 1 or 33.33% of respondents. The study is found to be adult based from the majority of the respondents.

Respondents Personal Profile According to Current Status

Variable	Respondents	%
Civil Status		
Single	22	73.33
Married	6	20
Widow / Widower	1	3.33
Seperated	1	3.33
Total	30	100

Figure 4.3 shows the representation of how the respondents were distributed according to their civil status. The data shows that the highest respondents are single who got 22 or 73.33%. It is followed by the married with 6 or 20% of respondents and widow/widower which has 1 or 3.33%. Lastly, the least numbers of respondents are separated with 1 or 3.33 percent of the respondents. This is due to the fact that majority of users of cosmetics are single.

Respondents' Personal Profile According to Educational Background

Variable	Respondents	%
Educational Background		
No formal education	0	0
Elementary Graduate	0	0
High School Graduate	5	16.66
Vocational Graduate	2	6.66
College Undergraduate	17	56.66
College Graduate	6	20
Total	30	100

Figure 4.4 shows the representation of how the respondents were distributed according to their educational background. The data shows that got a highest percentage are College undergraduate which has 17 or 56.66% of respondents. It is followed by the College graduate with 6 or 20% of respondents and high school graduate with 5 or 16.66%, and also the vocational graduate with 2 or 6.66% of respondents and no one of the respondents to No formal education and Elementary Graduate. This demonstrates that the majority of the respondents are College undergraduate.

Respondents' Personal Profile According to Current Status

Variable	Respondents	%
Current Status		
Student	17	56.66
Housewife	2	6.66
Employee	8	26.66
Others	3	10
Total	30	100

Figure 4.5 shows the representation of how the respondents were distributed according to their current status. The data shows that the respondents for students have 17 or 56.66%. It is followed by the employee with 8 or 26.66% of respondents and others which has 3 or 10%. Lastly, the least number of scored is the housewife with 2 or 6.66%. The means that the majority of the respondents are Students.

Discussion of Results for Research Question 1

How do respondents identify the original product from counterfeit in terms of price, packaging and product texture?

Table 4.6 presents the difference of the original product from the counterfeit base on the answers of the respondents from selected barangay of Quezon City

Difference of Two Product			
Variables	WM	Interpretation	Rank
Indicators			
Price	2.66	MA	3
Packaging	3.6	A	2
Product Texture	3.7	A	1
Total	3.32	A	

Legends:

HA – Highly Agree

A – Agree

MA – Moderately Agree

MD – MD – Moderately Disagree

D – Disagree

Interpretation:

4.50 – 5.00 – Highly Agree

3.50 – 4.00 – Agree

2.50 – 3.00 – Moderately Agree

2.00 – 1.50 – Moderately Disagree

1.50 – 1.00 – Disagree

The data in table 4.6 demonstrate the difference of two products which are considered to be necessary indicators to identify the original product and counterfeit product. The data result shows that the highest scored is the “Product texture” which has computed mean of 3.7 interpreted as Agree and ranked top 1 among the identify the original product from the counterfeit product. The result presents that respondents felt skin irritation, roughness of the product and the color that causes disease. It is followed by rank 2 which is labeled as “Packaging” calculated mean of 3.6 interpreted as Agree, among its indicators the respondents do not know what is the difference of the product like how to indicates the barcode, specific active ingredients, shows address of the manufacturer and registered trademark because the packaging are same as the original than to counterfeit product. The genuine company putting ingredients in their secret area where the customer does not know that a company has a secret mark that does not work with other businesses especially the counterfeiters. Lastly, the “Price” with a mean of 2.66 interpreted as Moderately Agree which got a third rank. Other consumers purchasing an item because of the low price. They don’t know if it is original or counterfeit as long as they can purchase a product and get along with the trend. So many people still do not know how to identify the product they buy. The overall total results are interpreted as Agree since the total weighted mean is 3.32. Therefore, these results will help in this study especially to the consumer to identify the products.

Discussion of Results for Research Question 2

What are the measures to educate about the original and counterfeit product?

Table 4.7 Presents the measure to educate the unaware customer by buying a product if it is original or not.

Measures to Educate

Variables	WM	Interpretation	Rank
Indicators			
Advertisement	2.7	MA	1
Seminar	2.63	MA	2
Personal Selling	2.3	MD	3
Total	2.54	MA	

Legends:

HA – Highly Agree

A – Agree

MA – Moderately Agree

MD – MD – Moderately Disagree

Disagree

D – Disagree

Interpretation:

4.50 – 5.00 – Highly Agree

3.50 – 4.00 – Agree

2.50 – 3.00 – Moderately Agree

2.00 – 1.50 – Moderately

1.50 – 1.00 – Disagree

The findings of table 4.7 display the measure to educate the consumer about the original and counterfeit product which can help to the consumer to be aware about this fraudulent selling. The data result shows that the rank 1 is the “Advertisement” with the highest calculated mean of 2.7 interpreted as Moderately Agree. The result show that the respondents want to educate the unaware customer through Social Media, TV Commercial and Tarpaulin to avoid purchasing prohibited frauds. It is followed by rank 2 “Seminar” which has computed mean of 2.63 and also interpreted as Moderately Agree because the respondents want to conduct seminar to the employees and customers to give product information as well as to give free orientation for the resellers about what to do if they are encounter counterfeiting. The rank 3 is “Personal Selling” which was interpreted as Moderately Disagree with a mean of 2.3, because there are people who are not using an appliance or employees who are not using gadgets and do not know what is happening in the world like widening the scope of counterfeiting, where they can be taught from house to house promotion, actual testing of two products given to the schools, offices and malls and give a demo to the customers. The overall total results are interpreted as Moderately Agree since the total weighted mean is 2.54.

Discussion of Results for Research Question 3

What are the factors that influence the patronage of counterfeit products?

Table 4.8 presents the factors that influence the patronage of counterfeiting product to the customers who are buying and making counterfeiting.

Influence the patronage

Variables	WM	Interpretation	Rank
Indicators			
Cost	2.46	MD	2
Accessibility	2.63	MA	1
Societal Perception	2.0	MD	3
Total	2.36	MD	

Legends:

HA – Highly Agree

A – Agree

MA – Moderately Agree

MD – MD – Moderately Disagree

Disagree

D – Disagree

Interpretation:

4.50 – 5.00 – Highly Agree

3.50 – 4.00 – Agree

2.50 – 3.00 – Moderately Agree

2.00 – 1.50 – Moderately

1.50 – 1.00 – Disagree

The given data in table 4.8 shows the factors that influence the patronage of counterfeiting to the customers. The table shows that the highest calculated mean of 2.63 is the “Accessibility” which interpreted as Moderately Agree. The results show that the respondents do not disagree because it is easy to sell to the consumer, the original product is too expensive for them to buy, and they can save more money. It is followed by rank 2 “Cost” with a mean of 2.46 interpreted as Moderately Disagree because of the increasing number of the counterfeit stores and manufacturers everywhere that can destroy the reputation of the genuine business and intellectual property of the owner. The reason why they are making fakes is small investment in producing the products, more productions other than original product and more products to produce than to capital. Lastly, the “Societal Perception” with a mean of 2.0 interpreted as Moderately Disagree that respondents felt sad when it comes to customers who are not aware of counterfeiting products even, they know it is not good for them because it is harmful especially to the sensitive skin. As long as they can purchase a product and get along with the trend. The overall total results are interpreted as Moderately Disagree as since the total weighted mean is 2.36.

DISCUSSION

Brand awareness strategy:

1. Observe if other business counterfeits the product.
2. Inform the employees to be aware of counterfeit by doing seminars and orientation.
3. Make plans of the company about brand awareness strategy by providing possible solution of management.
4. Start implementing the plan by providing the management of the date when the action is completed and start promoting branding awareness strategy.
5. Do weekly evaluation of the product. Continue to regularly check the market or malls that are selling counterfeit items.

	IDENTIFIED PROBLEM	POSSIBLE SOLUTION BY THE MANAGEMENT
Identify the Product <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product Texture • Packaging • Price 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Felt irritation because of the roughness and stickiness of the product and offensive smell. • Counterfeit and original are same packaging so that's why the customer does not know how to identify the original product. • The price of the counterfeit is too low than the original. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of new active ingredient that is hard to produce by those who counterfeit yet give benefits to the customer especially to the sensitive skin • Tell all the employees to prevent counterfeit by create new design where there is a secret mark in the packaging. • Implement marketing plans such promotions so that the customer can buy the original product.
Measure to educate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advertisement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not aware of purchasing items because there is no 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The management should provide

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminar • Personal Selling 	<p>advertising about counterfeiting awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It does not have a seminar that is why consumers do not have awareness of counterfeit • It is too complacent that no one has counterfeit their product so they do not give awareness to customer 	<p>advertisement to educate the customer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The company will conduct seminar to prevent counterfeit every 6 months • The management gives actual testing of two products of their differences.
<p>Influence to patronage the counterfeit product</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It's not hard for them to sell the counterfeit product 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All counterfeit products shall be confiscated or removed to the market to prevent customers from buying counterfeit product.

Conclusions

The following conclusion is based on the assumption of this study.

1. Consumers were not aware about counterfeit product because they don't know what will be the effect to them especially on the genuine companies that provide real-time service to customers.

2. The measure to educate people about counterfeit is to help and educate people especially on unaware customers, how they will know and be aware about the difference between counterfeit from the original.

3. The factor that influence the patronization of counterfeit product is small investment in producing the products, more productions other than original product and more product to produce than capital. .

4. A well- established brand awareness strategy can be a great source of genuine company and customer by purchasing of product so they know how to choose a product and be aware about counterfeit product.

Recommendations

On the basis of the conclusion and the findings, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. The company should know first what is happening in the market and identify the product by comparing with original and counterfeit product. They must inform the staff and employees before take an action to lessen the manufacturers of counterfeit product.

2. The company must educate and help the customer by conducting seminars, orientation to be aware of purchasing items.

3. The company should implement and confiscate the counterfeit products selling in the market. All stores must have permitted proving that their product they are selling is original.

4. Based on the findings, the strategies to developed is company must know the problems they are encountered especially counterfeit products, they need to take an action and they to take effective strategies to become aware of counterfeit products

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to participating in any data collection activities, all participants were provided with clear and comprehensive information about the purpose of the study, the nature of their involvement, and any potential risks or benefits. Participants provided informed consent voluntarily and were assured of their anonymity and confidentiality.

The confidentiality of participants' personal information and responses was strictly maintained throughout the research process. All data collected were anonymized and stored securely to prevent unauthorized access or disclosure.

The research was conducted with honesty, integrity, and objectivity, without any bias or conflict of interest. The findings and conclusions presented in the study accurately reflect the data collected and are not influenced by any external factors.

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REFERENCES

- Bian, X. and Moutinho, L. (2011), "The role of brand image, product involvement, and knowledge in explaining consumer purchase behaviour of counterfeits: Direct and indirect effects", *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 45 No. 1/2, pp. 191-216.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/03090561111095658>
- Crettez, Bertrand & Hayek, Naïla & Zaccour, Georges. (2018). Brand imitation: A dynamic-game approach. *International Journal of Production Economics*. 205. 10.1016/j.ijpe.2018.09.010.
- Jiang, Ji & Chen, Jin. (2021). Managing the Product-Counterfeiting Problem with a Blockchain-Supported E-Commerce Platform. *Sustainability*. 13. 6016. 10.3390/su13116016.
- Jyani, N. and Bansal, H. (2022), "Alibaba: the battle against counterfeits", , Vol. 12 No. 1. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EEMCS-05-2021-0162>
- Ramos, Christine Mary, Vol. 3 No. 2I (2019): *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*.
- Spink, J., Moyer, D.C., Park, H. et al. Defining the types of counterfeiters, counterfeiting, and offender organizations. *Crime Sci* 2, 8 (2013).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/2193-7680-2-8>